

Using Reinforcement Learning to Weaken DDoS Attacks in Real-Time

Abdelrahman Lasheen

Abstract

Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks represent an increasing risk to cyber security, with their frequency and impact on the rise each day, causing significant disruptions by flooding or overloading the online servers. Typical mitigation techniques such as rate limiting and firewall often do not work as these attacks are dynamic and constantly changing. Reinforcement Learning (RL) was used for this research as it outperforms traditional mitigation methods. Unlike traditional machine learning methods, RL continuously learns and improves its strategies through interaction with the environment, making it particularly effective against the ever-changing threats. This study evaluates the effectiveness of RL in providing a robust, adaptive defense mechanism, offering insights into its potential to transform network security systems.

Index Terms: DDoS Mitigation, Reinforcement Learning, DDoS Attacks, Machine Learning, Cyber Security

1 Introduction

Over the years, a wide variety of attacks have targeted online apps and services. One of them is Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks which might stop or postpone the services, causing financial crisis or reputation damage for the target. DDoS attacks work by overloading a server; therefore, it becomes challenging to users to access a specific website or internet service. Some examples of this threat include Smurf, Fraggle, and SYN Floods. In addition, this type of attack is so significant that even the biggest companies like Amazon and Google were not immune to them (Riyan Hakak and Ahmad, 2021).

Since DDoS attacks are becoming more complex and dynamic, traditional defense techniques are no longer effective (Wang, Wang and Wang, 2023). Rate limiting, fire wall, and blackholing are all types of traditional prevention techniques (Mahjabin et al., 2017). Additionally, some companies even develop a response plan or increase their bandwidth to accommodate unexpected spikes (Feinstein et al., 2003). These methods fall short as they often have limited scalability, slow response time, and they cannot keep up with the

continuously changing attack patterns. Hence why machine learning methods are used instead.

While machine learning techniques tend to be the best option for this issue, there are still some drawbacks, such as high false positive rates and trouble managing various attack types (Sadhvani et al., 2023). This is when Reinforcement Learning (RL) is gaining attention. Reinforcement Learning is a type of machine learning that trains software to make decisions that lead to optimal results (Kanade, 2022). It also focuses on decision making using autonomous agents. Any system that can make decisions and respond to its surroundings without human coordination is considered an autonomous agent (Gordana Dodig-Crnkovic and Burgin, 2024). Robots and driverless vehicles are examples of autonomous agents. Through trial and error, autonomous agents also learn how to function without human direction (IBM, Murel and Kavlakoglu, 2024).

This research explores the application of Reinforcement Learning to mitigate DDoS attacks in real-time. The goal is to provide new perspectives on adaptive security techniques and enhance the understanding of dynamic response strategies within network security, while comparing several papers (Li, 2024).

2 Literature Review

The constantly increasing popularity of internet usage increases the possibility of advanced and

powerful DDoS attacks (Singh and Gupta, 2022), which create significant problems for online businesses and services. DDoS attacks use a huge number of malicious devices to flood and overflow networks (AAMIR and ZAIDI, 2013). Recent research areas have focused on different approaches to preventing DDoS attacks, such as the usage of a distributed system, smart traffic filters, and proactive attack prediction tools (Kalkan and Alagöz, 2016). This literature review focuses on several research papers that address this issue in depth, as well as how reinforcement learning may help reduce it. In addition, the literature review contains research aims, methods, experimental results and researcher conclusions.

2.1 Per-Host DDoS Mitigation by Direct-Control Reinforcement Learning (Simpson et al., 2020)

Simpson et al., (2020) focused on addressing Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) through an application of Reinforcement Learning (RL). Standard approaches are ineffective in dealing with the evolving nature of DDoS attacks. These attacks constantly evolve and adapt to new protocols and network configurations. Simpson et al., (2020) highlight two RL-based models which are Instant Control and Guarded Control, that aim to dynamically manage network flows to improve performance and lessen the impact of DDoS attacks on legitimate traffic.

Extensive experiments with simulated network environments were conducted to validate their approach. The performance of RL models was compared against the current methods, including the state-of-the-art Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) model. In addition, the experiments were conducted with different network topologies, UDP and TCP as traffic types, and host densities to test the effectiveness of the model. These results show that, in terms of retaining network speed and protecting valid traffic, new RL models outperformed traditional methods. Moreover, the research showed detailed findings, including the number of typical rewards protected by how much traffic. These examples show that the new models are more adaptable to many scenarios than previous models.

The experimental methods used were valid, involving detailed tests that were like real world problems, hence it was realistic. By varying traffic types, host densities, and network topologies, Simpson et al., (2020) ensured a robust evaluation of their models' performance. The single and multi-destination topology usage provided a complete understanding of the model's capabilities in many different scenarios.

The results supported the researchers' claims by showing how RL models, especially guarded control, outperformed traditional DDoS prevention methods. The presented data, including reward metrics and learning curves, clearly demonstrated the model's effectiveness in mitigating DDoS attacks and protecting legitimate traffic. While most of the claims were appropriate, the researchers mentioned some drawbacks, such as long training sessions and possible problems with local optima. In general, the research shows the potential of RL approaches in improving network security and provides suggestions for further enhancements, investigating more types of attacks.

2.2 DDoS Attack Detection using Machine Learning Techniques in Cloud Computing Environments (Zekri et al., 2017)

Zekri et al., (2017) focused their study on designing a system that detects DDoS attacks which are derived from C4.5 machine learning algorithm to strengthen security in cloud computing environments. Furthermore, this research targets the fixing of the gaps in the cloud systems usually targeted by attackers to launch DDoS attacks. The C4.5 algorithm has been used for the development of a decision tree to identify and mitigate DDoS attacks automatically. This approach was selected to achieve high detection accuracy and faster response times. Zekri et al., (2017) have compared the performance of the proposed C4.5-based detection system against other machine learning techniques like Naive Bayesian and K-Means. Additionally, simulations were performed in a virtual environment using OpenStack Juno and Oracle Virtual Box, and DDoS attacks were generated by Hping3. It showed outstanding performance that achieved 98.8% detection accuracy in 0.58 seconds, which outperformed other methods, as

shown in tableII. The authors concluded that their proposed approach provided a strong and efficient DDoS detection solution and planned further development to extend it toward a real-time detection system.

TABLE II
DDoS ATTACK DETECTION RESULT IN DIFFERENT DURATION

Method used	Correct Classification (%)	Detection Time (S)
Naive Bayesian	91.4	1.25
C4.5	98.8	0.58
K-Means	95.9	1.12

The methods appear to be appropriate, as the work was based on heavy experimentation that included several machine learning algorithms and a controlled virtual environment. Results showed the efficiency of the C 4.5 algorithm in the detection of DDoS attacks with high accuracy and lower detection time, which was expected from the findings by the researchers themselves.

Beyond that, evidence clearly describes the case presented and shows how such a C4.5-based system would work by detecting DDoS reliably in cloud environments. What I conclude from here is that this research adds value toward cloud security.

2.3 Deep Reinforcement Learning based Smart Mitigation of DDoS Flooding in Software-Defined Networks (Liu et al., 2018)

Liu et al., (2018) addressed the big issue of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) that has plagued the internet for decades. Liu et al., (2018) described the attack as a “destructive threat” for the internet. Hence, Liu et al. (2018) sought to create an innovative, real-time mitigation framework using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) within a Software Defined Network (SDN). They aimed to use centralized control in the whole network to make wise decisions to distinguish between clean and attack traffic and optimize the mitigation strategies accordingly.

Liu et al., (2018) did several experiments to evaluate the proposed DRL-based mitigation methodology. They produced various patterns for DDoS attacks, including consistent rate, escalating rate, pulse attacks, and group-based attacks. Their system was tested against a range of popular techniques like AIMD router

throttling and CTL methods. In their results, it was found that their approach was offering better service availability and efficient attack traffic throttling compared to existing solutions. Graphs were plotted both for enhanced benign traffic performance and reduced attack traffic in different attack scenarios, with tables presented to support performance benefits.

The findings of this study showed that the proposed DRL system efficiently mitigates DDoS attacks, responding to attack changing aspects, while ensuring service availability for real users. Moreover, the dependency of the system on standardized OpenFlow APIs renders compatibility with current SDN infrastructure.

Fig. 4. Performance for unseen DDoS attack types

The experimental technique used in this study appears to be robust, as it uses realistic simulation environments and a variety of DDoS attack types to validate the DRL-based approach. The use of TensorFlow to implement the framework and Mininet to create virtual hosts results in a feasible and scalable testing configuration.

The results convincingly prove how the proposed DRL-based system enhances resilience against DDoS attacks, presenting comprehensive graphs and statistical data in support.

In conclusion, the research proved that the proposed DRL-based framework is a significant advancement in DDoS mitigation. The methods used are valid, the results stand in support of the claims made, and the overall findings provide a promising solution to improve network security against evolving cyber threats.

2.4 DDoS Mitigation while Preserving QoS: A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Approach (Shurok Khozam et al., 2024)

Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) researched the effectiveness of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) in reducing DDoS attacks while maintaining Quality of Service (QoS) in 5G networks that depend significantly on Software-Defined Networking (SDN). The researchers were mostly motivated by the fact that traditional cybersecurity methods are not good enough to handle the changing and complex nature of modern cyber threats, especially in virtualized environments like SDNs. The researchers propose a framework based on the Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) in their project, which “is an improvement to the Deep Q-Learning (DQN) algorithm aimed at mitigating the overestimation issue inherent in DQN” as Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) stated. Defense strategies in this model are personalized in such a way as to suit any kind of DDoS attacks and situations from the attacks, even in the worst-case scenario.

Fig. 4. System Architecture.

Regarding the experimental settings, Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) stated “Our SDN network is implemented using the Mininet emulator3 with a customized controller as depicted in Fig. 4. Mininet provides a virtualized environment for network emulation, allowing us to create and simulate various network scenarios” where various forms of DDoS attacks, including ICMP, TCP, SYN, and UDP floods, were emulated. The performance indicators, including latency, jitter, and throughput, were carefully observed to assess the viability and effectiveness of the suggested solution. The results showed a significant fall in QoS

violation and improved network performance for legitimate users. The conclusion reached was that the proposed DRL framework could effectively mitigate DDoS attacks while preserving QoS, with potential for further scalability and optimization.

Experiments and methods used for this study seem valid, since the simulation setup is well done, with real-time monitoring of real attack situations. The results, presented through graphs and tables, are as claimed by researchers to improve network performance, such as lower delays and better data flow. Overall, the research strongly shows evidence of the capability of DRL for network security and performance enhancement, though more work is needed to make it better and more widely usable.

3 Evaluation and Discussion

3.1 Compare and Contrast

The reviewed literature presents a spectrum of approaches to mitigating DDoS attacks, each with its unique strengths and limitations. Simpson et al., (2020) did a reinforcement learning approach by instant and guarded control models, showing significant flexibility and adaptability in different environments. Both models excel in maintaining network performance and defending genuine traffic, which makes them helpful against the growing DDoS threats. Zekri et al. (2017) proposed an alternative approach for detecting DDoS attacks by employing the c4.5 algorithm for decision trees, demonstrating high accuracy and speed in its performance.

On the other hand, Liu et al. (2018) and Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) point out the use of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). Liu et al., (2018) attention was on real time DDoS mitigation in Software Defined Networks (SDN), showing significant improvements in attack management. While, Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) extend this to 5G networks, using a Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) to handle the overestimation problem, maintaining Quality of Service (QoS) alongside effective DDoS mitigation.

Among the five papers presented Shurok Khozam et al., (2024) seem to have the best

framework. Concentrating on maintaining QoS in 5G networks while effectively avoiding DDoS attacks ensures both their security and performance, which is crucial. In addition, the Double Deep Q-Network that they use also resolves overestimation issues common in DRL, enhancing the reliability of their approach.

3.2 Wider implications

These theories have wide implications in different fields. For businesses, these new approaches to RL and DRL may translate into network resilience, reduced downtime, and protection against the financial losses of DDoS attacks (Tuomas Haarnoja et al., 2018). To programmers and software engineers, this is a field with many opportunities to design more sophisticated and adaptive security systems that need to learn and be updated constantly to meet the demands of cybersecurity challenges.

These DDoS mitigation advances contribute to global cybersecurity, especially in this increasingly critical digital world, therefore it means making sure that essential services remain stable and reliable. Integration of RL and DRL shall be considered in dynamic threat environments where traditional methods fail to provide protection (Mnih et al., 2015). On the other hand, these methods may not suit static or low complexity environments due to their complexity (Arulkumaran et al., 2017).

Finally, the suitability of classic machine learning algorithms such as C4.5 is retained only in specific domains (Cherfi, Noura and Ferchichi, 2018), whereas both RL and DRL have developed better edges regarding the evolving cyber threats and thus are selected to handle advanced challenges in network security (Nguyen and Reddi, 2021).

4 Conclusion

This research has discussed the application of Reinforcement Learning to real-time mitigation in DDoS attacks and has represented a big change in network security. By deeply reviewing the related literature and experimental studies, the findings clearly establish that RL can prove to be a better strategy than any traditional DDoS mitigation techniques.

Evidence from various studies point out the adaptability and robustness of Reinforcement Learning in response to DDoS threats (Alashhab et al., 2024). Unlike traditional methods that usually fail in evolving attack patterns, RL is always learning from its environment, hence enhancing its defense mechanism over time (Imad Tareq et al., 2024). This adaptive learning capability allows for more effective identification and mitigation of attacks, ensuring higher resilience and network stability.

A comparative study of various RL models, including those with Deep Reinforcement Learning, highlights the diverse strategies and enhancements made in this area. For example, the overestimation issue that has been targeted by using DDQN is so important (Hessel et al., 2018). These will be further improved by increasing detection and response times, which might enhance the Quality of Service (QoS) in complex network environments, such as those of 5G.

This research has also shown that it is easy to integrate RL-based frameworks into existing infrastructures for scalability and automation of DDoS mitigation strategies. Such integrations will ensure that the success of businesses and service providers protects their digital assets against evolving cyber threats (Docas Akinleye and Godwin, 2024).

In conclusion, it is crystal clear from the above results that the contribution has not only benefited academia but also shed light on network security improvements for realistic applications. This underlines the importance of further exploration and refinement of RL-based solutions.

5 Future Work

The future research could be directed to the advanced reinforcement learning techniques, including deep reinforcement learning and multi-agent systems, for enhanced decision-making in dynamic network environments. Scaling the proposed solution to large real-world deployments and diverse network types, including IoT and 5G, would add much value to determining its effectiveness and adaptability. Besides, the integration of the RL-based system with other security mechanisms, such as anomaly detection and traditional DDoS

mitigation techniques, may provide a more complete defense strategy. Further investigation into adaptive and personalized defense mechanisms and optimizing the system for real-time low latency performance remains a critical area for future work.

References

1. Riyan Hakak and Ahmad, M. (2021). Automatic Defense Against Distributed Denial of Service Using Anomaly Based Method in Machine Learning. *2021 Third International Conference on Intelligent Communication Technologies and Virtual Mobile Networks (ICICV)*. [online] doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/icicv50876.2021.9388548>.
2. Wang, J., Wang, L. and Wang, R. (2023). A Method of DDoS Attack Detection and Mitigation for the Comprehensive Coordinated Protection of SDN Controllers. *Entropy (Basel, Switzerland)*, [online] 25(8), p.1210. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/e25081210>.
3. Mahjabin, T., Xiao, Y., Sun, G. and Jiang, W. (2017). A survey of distributed denial-of-service attack, prevention, and mitigation techniques. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, [online] 13(12), p.155014771774146. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1550147717741463>.
4. Kanade, V. (2022). What Is Reinforcement Learning? Working, Algorithms, and Uses. [online] Spiceworks. Available at: <https://www.spiceworks.com/tech/artificial-intelligence/articles/what-is-reinforcement-learning/>.
5. IBM, Murel, J. and Kavlakoglu, E. (2024). Reinforcement Learning. [online] Ibm.com. Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/reinforcement-learning>.
6. Gordana Dodig-Crnkovic and Burgin, M. (2024). A Systematic Approach to Autonomous Agents. *Philosophies*, 9(2), pp.44–44. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophie9020044>
7. Simpson, K.A., Rogers, S.N. and Pezaros, D.P. (2020). Per-Host DDoS Mitigation by Direct-Control Reinforcement Learning. *Per-Host DDoS Mitigation by Direct-Control Reinforcement Learning*, 17(1), pp.103–117. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/tnsm.2019.2960202>.
8. Liu, Y., Dong, M., Ota, K., Li, J. and Wu, J. (2018). Deep Reinforcement Learning based Smart Mitigation of DDoS Flooding in Software-Defined Networks. 2018 IEEE 23rd International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/camad.2018.8514971>.
9. Shurok Khozam, Blanc, G., Sébastien Tixeuil and Totel, E. (2024). DDoS Mitigation while Preserving QoS: A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Approach. [online] doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/netsoft60951.2024.10588889>.
10. Zekri, M., Kafhali, S.E., Aboutabit, N. and Saadi, Y. (2017). DDoS attack detection using machine learning techniques in cloud computing environments. [online] IEEE Xplore. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/CloudTech.2017.8284731>
11. Tuomas Haarnoja, Zhou, A., P. Abbeel and Levine, S. (2018). Soft Actor-Critic: Off-Policy Maximum Entropy Deep Reinforcement Learning with a Stochastic Actor. [online] International Conference on Machine Learning. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Soft-Actor-Critic%3A-Off-Policy-Maximum-Entropy-Deep-Haarnoja-Zhou/811df72e210e20de99719539505da54762a11c6d>
12. Mnih, V., Kavukcuoglu, K., Silver, D., Rusu, A.A., Veness, J., Bellemare, M.G., Graves, A., Riedmiller, M., Fidjeland, A.K., Ostrovski, G., Petersen, S., Beattie, C., Sadik, A., Antonoglou, I., King, H., Kumaran, D., Wierstra, D., Legg, S. and Hassabis, D. (2015). Human-level Control through Deep Reinforcement Learning. *Nature*, 518(7540), pp.529–533. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14236>.
13. Arulkumaran, K., Deisenroth, M.P., Brundage, M. and Bharath, A.A. (2017). Deep Reinforcement Learning:

- A Brief Survey. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 34(6), pp.26–38. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/msp.2017.2743240>.
14. Cherfi, A., Nouira, K. and Ferchichi, A. (2018). Very Fast C4.5 Decision Tree Algorithm. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 32(2), pp.119–137. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08839514.2018.1447479>.
 15. Singh, A. and Gupta, B.B. (2022). Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) Attacks and Defence Mechanisms in Various Web-enabled Computing Platforms. *International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems*, 18(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.4018/ijswis.297143>.
 16. AAMIR, M. and ZAIDI, M.A. (2013). A Survey on DDoS Attack and Defense Strategies: From Traditional Schemes to Current Techniques. *Interdisciplinary Information Sciences*, 19(2), pp.173–200. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4036/iis.2013.173>.
 17. Imad Tareq, Bassant Mohamed Elbagoury, Salsabil Amin El-Regaily and El-Horbaty, E.-S.M. (2024). Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach for Cyberattack Detection. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (iJOE)*, [online] 20(05), pp.15–30. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v20i05.48229>.
 18. Sadhwani, S., Baranidharan Manibalan, Raja Muthalagu and Pawar, P.M. (2023). A Lightweight Model for DDoS Attack Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques. *Applied sciences*, 13(17), pp.9937–9937. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/app13179937>.
 19. Feinstein, L., Schnackenberg, D., Balupari, R. and Kindred, D. (2003). Statistical approaches to DDoS attack detection and response. [online] *IEEE Xplore*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/DISCEX.2003.1194894>.
 20. Kalkan, K. and Alagöz, F. (2016). A distributed filtering mechanism against DDoS attacks: ScoreForCore. *Computer Networks*, 108, pp.199–209. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2016.08.023>.
 21. Nguyen, T.T. and Reddi, V.J. (2021). Deep Reinforcement Learning for Cyber Security. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 34(8), pp.1–17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/tnnls.2021.3121870>.
 22. Alashhab, A.A., M. Soperi Zahid, Babangida Isyaku, Asma Abbas Elnour, Wamda Nagmeldin, Abdelzahir Abdelmaboud, Talal A.A. Abdullah and Umar Maiwada (2024). Enhancing DDoS Attack Detection and Mitigation in SDN using an Ensemble Online Machine Learning Model. *IEEE access*, pp.1–1. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2024.3384398>.
 23. Hessel, M., Modayil, J., Van Hasselt, H., Schaul, T., Ostrovski, G., Dabney, W., Horgan, D., Piot, B., Azar, M. and Silver, D. (2018). Rainbow: Combining Improvements in Deep Reinforcement Learning. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 32(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v32i1.11796>.
 24. Docas Akinleye and Godwin, O. (2024). Optimizing SDN-Based DDoS Mitigation Using Machine Learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. [online] doi:<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4980289>.
 25. Li, Y. (2024). Research on Bionic Robot Motion Control Based on Reinforcement Learning. *Highlights in Science Engineering and Technology*, [online] 114, pp.73–78. doi:<https://doi.org/10.54097/wtrmgm41>.